

The Impact of Whatsapp Messenger usage on Students Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to empirically identify the impact of social network (what Sapp messenger) on the performance of students in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre from the perspective of the students. To achieve this, data was collected with help of structured questionnaire from 60 students of MBA and B. Architecture from same institute. The study revealed that, what Sapp instead of making communication easier and faster thereby enhancing effective flow of information and idea sharing among students, rather has impacted negatively on the performance of students. The study among students unveiled that what Sapp takes much of students study time, results in procrastination related problems, destroys students' spellings and grammatical construction of sentences, leads to lack of concentration during lectures, results in difficulty in balancing online activities (what Sapp) and academic preparation and distracts students from completing their assignments and adhering to their private studies time table.

KEYWORD: *What Sapp Messenger, Usage, Impact, Students Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

These days it seems hard to escape the presence of technology. Most people will praise the many technological gadgets that they use in their everyday lives. Many of us depend on it to get us through the day, to do our job, to get around, and to find certain things. Technology is evolving at a very fast rate, and what most people did not even think could be real a few years ago, is now becoming a reality. What Sapp is one of the changes in technology that is commonly used on specific mobile phones and computers? Since

the Smart phones became popular, many messaging services were launched but What Sapp has become very popular among them. This Application is highly addictive and can create a great impact on regular users, and apart from that it can leave a trace that becomes difficult to control and cure. Some of the most prominent technological innovations are smart phones, laptops and using the internet. They have greatly affected many aspects of our lives. Today the Internet continues to grow day by day at an incredible speed. The research examines the effect of the What Sapp messenger and the invading technology represented in the use of personal computers and Smartphone on the behavior of students and their academic performance in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre. The subjects of interest about the students are their friendships and social lives, family relations, general health and personal achievements on campus. What Sapp Messenger has been around for a while but recent updates have improved the functionality of the application since its release date. The main purpose behind this application is to replace SMS with a cross platform mobile messenger that works on an internet data plan. If you have unlimited text, it is still beneficial as it is a convenient way to skip international fees that carriers may charge. It is currently available for I Phone, Android, Windows Phone, Nokia, Samsung, Blackberry etc. It is popular because there is no cost to message friends and family other than the internet data plan that user already have on their phones. It is easy to get started. Simply enter the telephone number of the device into the app. It then sorts through the contacts (with your permission) on the phone to figure out who else also has the app already installed. Users can then invite more contacts

or go ahead and start sending messages to the ones that the app discovered. The What Sapp messenger was purposely created by Brian Acton and Jan Koum (2009) to make communication and the distribution of multimedia messaging more easily and faster. In as much as the application brings us so many benefits, it has also got its flaws that are currently causing more harm than good among the students today. In cognizance of the rate at which our youth are hooking up to social media, there is the need to educate them on its advantages and disadvantages in their academic performance accordingly.

Objectives:

The preliminary study examines the use of What Sapp Messenger amongst students at Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre. The researcher attempted to understand the perceived high-level of usage of social What Sapp Messenger amongst the students by looking at the intensity of its usage and how it affects their academic performance.

- The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the degree of the negative impact of the use of What Sapp Messenger on students' performance in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre.
- Also to determine the relationship between the use of the application and academic performance.
- And finally, some recommendations for overcoming these problems will be discussed.

Literature Review:

Literature review for this paper was covered on Social Media and students performance. Social media has become a growing phenomenon with many and varied definitions in public and academic use. Any activities where humans share stories and influence others can be considered social networking Nicholson,(2011). Social networking or media is a great forum for discussing mutual topics of interest, and perhaps even meeting or renewing acquaintances with other humans virtually. According to Greenwald (2009) and Deloitte (2009), 55% of employees visit a social media site at least once a week.

Definition of Social Media

Social media can be defined as forms of electronic communication through which users interact among people in which they create, freely share, exchange and discuss information, ideas, personal messages, and other content about each other and their lives using a multimedia mix of personal words, pictures,

videos and audio, utilizing online platforms while they are connected to the Internet Cox & Rethman, (2011). Since their appearance, social media have changed different aspects of people's lives. Social media that were emerged by the rise of Web 2.0 technologies are characterized by several significant features such as user generated content, online identity creation and relational networking Margo, (2012). According to Smith (2010), "Social media sites are virtual platforms for interactivity and information exchange ... where issues are debated and defined ... Social media users collaborate in content creation ..., are proactive in searching information ..., and value control in social media participation (p. 330)". Social media are also defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content" Kaplan & Heanlein, (2010, p.61). To consider some context of the ubiquitous nature of social media, Nielsen (2010) argues that social media accounts for nearly one-quarter of all internet activity, and LinkedIn has over 80 million professionals in over 200 countries. Other platforms such as Face book, Twitter, MySpace and YouTube are available for everyone; it was traditionally created to connect with individuals from all over the world to include employees, friends and families. However, as the number of users increase to millions, organizations are also trying to connect with employees more so than ever. Social Media has changed the way people around the globe communicate with one another. However social networking has existed right from the onset of humanity. The concept of social networking has evolved, much like other innovations, and is becoming increasingly sophisticated with advancements in technology Edosomwan, Prakasan, Kouame, Watson, & Seymour, (2011). Currently, there are hundreds of SNSs that can draw millions of people, with diverse technological affordances. Social network sites are web based services that enable individuals to construct a semi-profile within a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share connection with, views and go through their list of connections and those made by others within the system, although the nature and nomenclature of these connections has variation Boyd and Ellison, (2007). The ability of making it possible to meet new friends is not the major characteristics of social networking sites, but solely because the social network can be made evident due to the possibility it

had been made eloquent. The outcome of these relationships of individuals that would ideally not have met each other is made possible. Although it's not the real aim, and most times new connections are usually between —latent ties Hay, (2006), they already knew each other physically. On larger perspectives, on social network sites, members are not online with the intention of discovering new acquaintances but to interact with old friends which already exist on their list. To put in more words, the social networking as an important coordinating property of these sites is titled—Social Network Sites William et al, (2009).

Students and use of Social Networking Sites

Social Networking Site is a communication tool for members. This kind of platform was designed as a way for friends, family, or strangers to have discussions and interaction or be in contact with each other. It allows members to explore new opportunities and experiences. Social Networking Sites allow students to express themselves, communicate, and collect profiles that highlight their talents and experience. Students are increasingly utilizing these social networks for friends' news feeds, personal updates, events and activities, notes, and messages. According to an extensive study by the Office of Communications (Of com) of the United Kingdom, almost half (49%) of children aged 8-17 who used the Internet had set up their own profiles on a social networking site Of com, (2008a); Dowd all, (2009). Positive perceptions obtained from users of social networking sites i.e. effective learning which has resulted in an easy learning climate among students Mazer, et al., (2010). In another study conducted by Keenan and Shirii, (2009) they explored how social networking sites encourage friendliness through the use of Face book, Twitter and LinkedIn.

Academic Performance

Tuck man (1975) defined performance as the apparent demonstration of understanding, concepts, skills, ideas and knowledge of a person and proposed that grades clearly depict the performance of a student. Hence, their academic performance must be managed efficiently keeping in view all the factors that can positively or negatively affect their educational performance. He proposed that internet is advantageous to both students and teachers if used as a tool of knowledge creation and dissemination. In addition, academic performance defined by Kobal and Musek, (2001) refers to the numerical scores of a

student's knowledge, representing the degree of a student's adaptation to school work and the educational system. Social media, Internet-based tools that promote collaboration and information sharing Junco, Helbergert, & Loken, (2011), can be used in academic settings to promote student engagement and facilitate better student learning Kabilan, Ahmad, & Abidin, (2010). Because student engagement represents the time and effort that students invest in collaborative and educational activities Kuh, (2001), it is often linked with the achievement of positive student learning outcomes, such as critical thinking and individual student development Carini, Kuh, & Klein, (2006); Kuh, (1993).

In the study conducted by Englander et al., (2010), he observed that students spend more time using SNSs for other purposes apart from educational use, thus affecting their academic performance. In another study Nalwa and Anand, (2003), shows that students like to use internet for their own responsibilities and this affects their academic performance. This study is further elaborated by Karpinski, (2009) where they stated that SNSs users had lower grade rankings than students who never engage in social interactions. However there are general benefits associated with users of SNSs. Roblyer et al., (2010) explained that SNSs are sources of communication among students and lecturers in their respective faculties. Furthermore, Kolek and Saunders, (2008) resolved that users of SNSs who are students have no effect whatsoever with their academic performance.

After a critical review of various literatures on social media, the researchers could identify that there are gaps in knowledge as far as the negative effect of the use of "What Sapp" and students' performance. This research also demonstrates the improvement in this area in some way, filling in gaps and adding to knowledge in and understanding of this particular field.

Methodology

Introduction

The idea behind this particular section is to reveal the rationale for the research methodology, the method and Strategy adopted in collecting data for the research. This part also seeks to reveal how the researchers conducted the research to be able to investigate the impact of social networks on the performance of students in Ideal Institute of

Management and Architecture, Kondigre with particular emphasis on What Sapp usage.

Research Methods

The researcher made use of both primary and secondary data, which were gathered from diverse sources, including, text books, journals/articles, and internet sites.

The primary research is tailored to suit the needs of the research. This research involves the collection of raw data, which forms the main basis for achieving the research objectives. An attempt was made at collecting and analyzing primary data which has gone a long way to validate the findings and conclusions drawn from the research. The qualitative research approach was deemed to be appropriate by the researchers hence its adoption. It has been observed that the use of multiple data collection methods, such as observation, interviews, document analysis and questionnaires are very important. With the importance of multiple sources of data very vital to the reliability of this research Stake, two primary sources of evidence were used: questionnaires, and interviews. The self-administered questionnaire method was employed because of its cost effective nature relative to interviews. Large number of participants can be involved and a lot of data collected in a relatively shorter time and at less cost. Although participants in this method are more likely to abandon the research in the course of responding, its privacy and anonymity promotes genuine answers. The less pressure on participants was also considered as a better way of convincing respondents to participate fully. With this method, interviewer biases are non-existent Gratton & Jones, (2004). However, problems can arise if questions are unclear, as the respondent cannot check what the researcher intended. A well-designed questionnaire was therefore important, especially ensuring that it was worded in simple English and an unambiguous manner to avoid this problem.

Sample Size

The population under-study consists of total 60 MBA & B.Arch. students in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre. The data was analyzed through the use of frequency tables.

Results and Discussion

This part analyses the responses given by respondents through the administration of structured questionnaire

and interview conducted. In order to make interpretation and analysis easier, tables are presented first, followed by its interpretation and analysis.

Table: Gender Distribution

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	40	66 %
Female	20	44 %
Total	60	100 %

Source: Survey data

The table above represents the number of students interviewed. Sixty students were interviewed from institution under study. Out of these, 66% represent male students while 44% were female. Out of the total number of students interviewed, 72 % of the interviewees said they use the what Sapp messenger on their phones for chatting with their friends on different issues instead of academic purposes on campus. They also mentioned that they use the application to send funny images to their colleagues. According to them the use of the application has negative impact on their studies.

Table: Reasons for Using What Sapp:

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
Academic Work	12	20 %
General Information	06	10 %
Chatting	30	50 %
Family	12	20 %
Total	60	100 %

Source: Survey data

Students were asked the reasons why they most often use what Sapp on their mobile phones. The results in the table above shows that majority of the students use the application for chatting with friends on different issues rather than academic work on campus, and this is represented by 50% of the total number of respondents. This also indicates the link between usage of the application and poor academic performance among the majority of the students. The more friends a student has on what Sapp, the more time he/she spends on the application” according to most students interviewed. A student who has a lot of friends on what Sapp is most likely going to be responding to more people and thus spending more time chatting. The study looked at students engaged in the use of the application for other purposes including academic work, general information, and family. The above table indicates that only 20% of the respondents use the application for academic work, 10% mainly

for general information while 20% use it for family issues.

Table: Time Spent On What Sapp:

Time	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	12	20 %
3-5	36	60 %
6-7	06	10 %
Over 8 hours	06	10 %
Total	60	100 %

Source: Survey data

The respondents reported the number of hours they spent using What Sapp per day. 20 % spent 1-2 hours, 60% spent 3-5 hours per day, 10% spent 6-7 hours and 06% spent more than 8 hours per day. The study shows an average student spends over 5-8 hours every day engaged in using what Sapp on their mobile phone. We were able to discover that there is an inverse relationship between two factors which is, the more time a student spends using what Sapp, the less time he or she has to attend to academic matters such as class work, assignments, preparation for class test, mid-semester exams and end of the semester's examination which account for the student's lower or poor grade Points. The more time a student spends on what Sapp, the "less likely they are to participate in class, thus according to most of the students we interviewed. If students bring their mobile phones to class, they get bored of the lesson and find their way onto what Sapp. These detracts their attention from the main lesson, and are not able to fully understand what is going on, hindering participation and drawing them even further into what Sapp making it more difficult for them at the end of the day.

Table: Students were asked whether What Sapp affect them positively or negatively in their studies

Effect	Frequency	Percentage
Positive	18	30 %
Negative	42	70 %
Total	60	100 %

Source: Survey data

As indicated in the table above, 70% percent of the respondents said the use of what Sapp has more negative effect on their studies and only 30% percent said it has positive impact on their studies. Most of them explained why they said it affects them negatively. A student can be stacked on his/her phone for hours chatting with friends through what Sapp without noticing the number of hours spent behind the phone not for any relevant reason. Little time is left

for academic purposes since much of their precious time is wasted on what Sapp chatting with friends. They later become less equipped and inadequately prepared for quizzes conducted and major end of semester examination which makes them less productive and effective. Procrastination-related problems are another negative effect on students' performance. One of the main questions that need to be asked is academic procrastination that might evolve as a possible outcome of What Sapp usage. Ellis and Knaus define this term as "a failure to initiate or complete a task or activity by predetermined time" (1977 cited in Sharma, 1997, pp. 17-18). In other words, it can be described as a specific behavioral pattern that is dedicated for doing any non-academic activities resulting in postponing completion of academic tasks (Sharma, 1997, p. 18). Most students also feel lazy typing most sentences and words and retire to the short hand form of typing. This style of writing destroys the students' spellings and grammatical construction of sentences. For example, word slike 'forward, come, tomorrow, goodnight' and others are being written as '4wrđ, kam, 2mrw, and gud9t etc,' also phrases like 'happy birthday' is being written as 'H.BDAY' Thank you is written as 'TY', WETHANK GOD is also written as 'WTG'. This has affected the way students write in English classes and in their examinations resulting in destruction of their grammar and the way they spell English words.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the preceding discussions, it is evidently clear that; what Sapp has been a necessary evil for students in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre. This stems from the fact that, it can enhance the performance of students if used positively. In that, it makes communication easier and faster thereby enhancing effective flow of information and idea sharing among students. However, if used negatively it has adverse impacts on the performance of students. Among the negative impacts we identified include the following: it takes much of the students studies time, results in procrastination related problems, destroys students grammar and spellings, leads to lack of concentration during lectures and difficulty in balancing online activities and academic preparation. Similar to most research, this paper has limitations that point to further opportunities. Although, framed within an academic context, the research can be utilized to investigate the use of What Sapp not only at colleges, but also at home,

workplace, and various other settings, and for a variety of different audiences such as teenagers, young adults, the elderly, or families. For future research, it may be more helpful to examine how a student's psychological state influences motivations for the use of What Sapp. In summary, the purpose of this paper was to identify the impact of what Sapp on the performance of students in Ideal Institute of Management and Architecture, Kondigre. The study found that, instead of making communication easier and faster thereby enhancing effective flow of messages and idea sharing among students, What Sapp has rather impacted negatively on the performance of students.

Recommendations:

The Researcher therefore, recommends the following:

- Management should intensify guidance and counselling sessions in their respective institutions.
- Time management should be incorporated into the curriculum.
- Unannounced quizzes should be conducted frequently by lecturers to compel students to sit-up.
- Cell phones should either be forbidden in lecture halls or switched off if allowed in, instead of the prevailing practice of allowing them in but must be put on mute.

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